

The cell uses Na⁺ and K⁺ to turn water into fuel

Johan Nygren

johanngrn@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: The cell combines three building blocks, a scaffold, an intracellular cation and an extracellular cation, into an “engine” that uses hydroxide ions as fuel. The hydroxide fuel is burnt in the reaction $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$, and powers the protein machinery of the cell. The building blocks of the machinery for this “engine” of life, have one purpose: to extract hydroxide ions as fuel by displacing hydrogen ions from the cell.

Introduction: a machine that burns hydroxide

There is one chemical reaction that releases electricity from water, $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$. This reaction is only favorable if the hydrogen ions that would tend to neutralize it are displaced. A machine that runs on water as fuel, would have to be able to physically exclude hydrogen ions. The evolution of such a machine is favoured by that water tends to spontaneously exclude H⁺, if there is a scaffold that promotes the gel-phase of water, (H₃O₂⁻)_n. This property exists in all gels.

This machine is further favoured if the gel (including the scaffold) prefers to associate with a monovalent cation other than H⁺, when other cations are available. Sidney Fox demonstrated in the 1980s that boiling amino acid polymers forms a gel that accumulates K⁺ to 1600 times the concentration in the medium (Fox, 1981; Matveev, 2016). In the case the substitute cation has a role in stabilizing the gel, then this machine would need to be able to expel the substitute cation to trigger the release of hydroxide ions. This hypothetical water-powered machine would need to rely on a different cation to displace H⁺ from the extracellular medium, so that the intracellular cation is free to leave during discharge of the hydroxide fuel supply.

The cell has all the properties of this hypothetical machine. It has a protein matrix scaffold to promote the gel-phase of water, it displaces H⁺ intracellularly with K⁺, and it displaces H⁺ extracellularly with Na⁺.

Turning on the engine, recharging the fuel

The hypothetical water-powered machine would ideally be able to turn its engine on and off at will. For this, the machine needs some type of on-off button or switch. It would also ideally be reusable, and have the ability to restore its fuel supply. In cells, these abilities are evident. Cells can transition from their resting potential, into a state of depolarization that is associated with the propagation of nerve impulses, or, contraction of muscle. And after a brief recharge, the activation can be repeated.

The cell is able to turn its engine on and off through the allosteric regulator ATP, that adjusts the ability of the protein scaffold to organize water into the gel-phase H_3O_2^- and to adsorb K^+ (Ling, 1962). ATP regulates the scaffold and intracellular cation, two traits of the hypothetical machine that favour the reaction $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$, and the cell charges its hydroxide fuel supply and restores its resting potential (Pollack, 2014) by recharging ATP once the engine is turned off.

K^+/H^+ exchange supports K^+ as a H^+ substitute

The role of K^+ as a substitute for H^+ intracellularly is evident from simple physiological observations. Extracellular acidosis leads to a release of K^+ from cells, H^+ is displacing the K^+ , and conversely, hyperkalemia leads to exit of H^+ from cells, resulting in intracellular alkalosis. These observations prove that K^+ and H^+ are competing, electrostatically, to be the conjugate cation of the gel-phase water, H_3O_2^- , and support the theory that the role of K^+ in the cell is to refine H_2O into OH^- by excluding H^+ .

References

Ishima, Y., Przybylski, A.T. & Fox, S.W. (1981). Electrical membrane phenomena in spherules from proteinoid and lecithin. *BioSystems* 13(4), 243–251.

Matveev, V. V. (2016). Comparison of fundamental physical properties of the model cells (protocells) and the living cells reveals the need in protophysiology. *International Journal of Astrobiology*, 16(1), 97–104. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1473550415000476>

Ling, G.N. (1962) *A Physical Theory of the Living State: the Association-Induction Hypothesis*. Blaisdell Publ. Co., Waltham, Mass

Pollack, G. H. (2014). Cell electrical properties: reconsidering the origin of the electrical potential. *Cell Biology International*, 39(3), 237–242. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbin.10382>